

Zinc Oxide as a general Sensitiser for Photochemical Reactions.

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If a system is not sensitive to light, it suffices at times to add to it a small quantity of another substance in order to make it sensitive to the action of rays absorbed by that substance. This action is known as *photochemical sensitisation* and the substance, which absorbs the light and provokes the reaction without apparently taking part in it, is called a *sensitiser*.

There is a class of photo-sensitisation in which a system which is chemically influenced by certain radiations is rendered sensitive to rays of another wave-length by a substance which absorbs these rays. Several years ago (Weigert, *Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1912, 80, 103) showed that ozone, which is decomposed by ultraviolet rays but not much by visible light is decomposed readily under the action of blue light when mixed with chlorine. Similarly in a foregoing paper (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1923, 128, 212), we have shown that the decomposition of Fehlings' solution, cupri-ammonium oxalate, Eder's mixture [HgCl_2 and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$], a mixture of mercuric chloride and a tartrate etc., can be markedly accelerated by ferric or uranyl salts under the influence of sunlight. Moreover, eosin, chlorophyll and several other substances have been used as sensitisers.

In a foregoing paper (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1926, 120, 302), we have explained photo-sensitisation from the point of view of the activation of molecules from the Franck-Cario point of view. For example, in the sensitisation of the decomposition of ozone in presence of chlorine, we can assume that by the absorption of blue light, the chlorine molecules get activated and such chlorine molecules are instrumental in bringing about the decomposition of ozone or the photochemical combination of hydrogen and oxygen in sunlight as observed by Norrish. Similarly, by the absorption of visible light, a molecule of chlorophyll is activated and this active molecule induces the chemical change between carbon dioxide and water vapour in plants.

In this investigation we have carried on numerous experiments with several photochemical reactions in presence of finely divided

zinc oxide as a sensitiser. We have observed that zinc oxide behaves as a very powerful sensitiser for several photochemical reactions.

In previous papers (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 134, 172; *Jour. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 926), we have shown that the velocity of sugar inversion in presence of acids is markedly accelerated by light and that inversion of cane sugar takes place in sunlight even in the absence of acids. We have now observed that sugar inversion and hydrolysis of maltose can be markedly accelerated by sunlight in presence of zinc oxide as a sensitiser.

The following reactions have been found to be sensitised by zinc oxide in presence of sun light:—(1) Decomposition of Fehlings' solution; (2) decomposition of cupri-ammonium oxalate; (3) formation of reducing sugars from formaldehyde; (4) formation of reducing sugars from glycerol; (5) oxidation of methyl or ethyl or propyl alcohol to the respective aldehyde by air; (6) formation of metallic gold from gold chloride; (7) formation of metallic platinum from platinum chloride; (8) oxidation of quinine sulphate by chromic acid; (9) oxidation of potassium iodide by potassium persulphate; (10) oxidation of sodium citrate by iodine; (11) oxidation of oxalic acid by iodine; (12) oxidation of potassium tartrate by iodine; (13) hydrolysis of maltose; (14) oxidation of sodium formate by iodine; (15) oxidation of iodoform; (16) oxidation of potassium tartrate by bromine; (17) oxidation of sodium nitrite by iodine; (18) oxidation of hydroxylamine hydrochloride by iodine; (19) oxidation of hydrazine hydrochloride by iodine; (20) oxidation of sodium formate by mercuric chloride; (21) oxidation of sodium sulphite by mercuric chloride; (22) oxidation of hydrazine hydrochloride by mercuric chloride; (23) oxidation of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ by mercuric chloride; (24) oxidation of potassium tartrate and mercuric chloride; (25) oxidation of sodium malate and mercuric chloride; (26) oxidation of potassium citrate and mercuric chloride; (27) oxidation of sodium lactate and mercuric chloride; (28) oxidation of sodium dichloroacetate and mercuric chloride; (29) decomposition of mercuric oxide; (30) decomposition of aqueous solutions of KMnO_4 ; (31) decomposition of potassium oxalate; (32) decomposition of aqueous solution of potassium persulphate.

The following reactions are also sensitized by substances other than ZnO but in all the reactions ZnO is the best sensitiser.

(1) Potassium tartrate and HgCl_2 —acceleration by ferric and ferrous chloride, KMnO_4 , uranium nitrate and Al_2O_3 .

(2) Sodium formate and HgCl_2 ,—in presence of Al_2O_3 and MnO_2 .

(3) Ammonium malonate + HgCl_2 ,—in presence of Al_2O_3 .

(4) Sodium malate + HgCl_2 ,—in presence of Al_2O_3 .

(5) Hydrazine hydrochloride + HgCl_2 ,—in presence of Al_2O_3 and erythrosin.

We have also investigated the effect of zinc oxide on the de-colourisation of solutions of dyes when exposed to sunlight. The solutions of the dyes were exposed to sunlight in dishes in presence of air. The concentrations of the dye solutions were obtained from the measurements of the extinction coefficients.

To determine the extinction coefficient the dye was kept in a glass cell and placed before a Nuttings spectro-photometer and the absorption was read on the density scale of the instrument. Knowing the thickness of the cell, the extinction coefficient was calculated by the formula, $\text{Extinction coeff.} = \frac{\text{Density Reading}}{\text{Thickness}}$

10 c.c. taken in a glass dish: 0.1 gm. of ZnO was added.

No.	Dyes.	Region in A Units.	Time. H. M.	Extinction coeff. unexposed (dark).	Extinction coeff. exposed (sunlight).	Extinction coeff. exposed with ZnO (sunlight).
A.	BLUE, VIOLET AND GREEN.					
1	Crystal Violet Do. + ZnO }	5560	1-30	2.759	2.624	0.180
2	Methylene Blue Do. + ZnO }	5560	1-0	1.065	0.805	Bleached.
3	Ethyl Green Do. + ZnO }	5560	1-30	2.293	2.104	0.180
4	Nile Blue Do. + ZnO }	5560	1-0	1.065	1.064	Bleached.
5	Asolitmin Do. + ZnO }	5840	1-0	1.851	1.899	0.005.

No.	Dyes.	Region in Å units.	Time H. M.	Extinction coeff. unexposed (dark).	Extinction coeff. exposed (sunlight).	Extinction coeff. exposed with ZnO (sunlight).
6	Aniline Blue } Do. + ZnO }	5880	1-0	5.558	2.442	0.897
7	Nigrosin } Do. + ZnO }	5840	1-0	1.299	1.299	0.180
8	Genatian Violet } Do. + ZnO }	5700	1-0	1.584	1.065	0.005
9	Malachite Green } Do. + ZnO }	5840	1-0	2.078	2.078	0.312
10	Methyl Violet } Do. + ZnO }	5040	1-0	0.805	0.727	0.104
11	Indigo Carmine } Do. + ZnO }	5040	1-0	0.779	0.779	0.156
12	Water Blue } Do. + ZnO }	5589	1-0	1.091	1.040	0.935
13	Allizarin Blue } Do. + ZnO }	5240	1-0	4.571	4.831	4.468
14	Cupric Blue } Do. + ZnO }	5360	1-0	1.351	1.247	0.935
15	Aniline Victorian Blue } Do. + ZnO }	5240	1-0	2.857	2.337	1.091
B.	FLUORESCENT DYES.					
16	Eosin } Do. + ZnO }	5520	1-45	1.506	0.571	0.026
17	Flourescein } Do + ZnO }	5200	1-45	1.114	0.649	0.104
18	Rhodamine } Do + ZnO }	5640	1-45	1.974	1.946	0.610
19	Erythrosine } Do + ZnO }	5480	1-45	3.686	2.208	0.727

No.	Dyes.	Region in Å units.	Time H. M.	Extinction coeff. unexposed (dark).	Extinction coeff. exposed (sunlight).	Extinction coeff. exposed with ZnO (sunlight).
20	Uranine } Do. + ZnO }	5360	1-45	1.117	1.065	0.779
21	Pyronine G. } Do. + ZnO }	5360	1-45	2.441	2.208	2.078
22	Acridine Red } Do. + ZnO }	5360	1-0	1.714	1.688	0.888
C.	RED YELLOW AND ORANGE.					
23	Rose Bengale } Do. + ZnO }	5920	2-30	1.506	1.851	1.273
24	Congo-Red } Do. + ZnO }	5840	2-30	1.558	1.558	0.987
25	Aurine } Do. + ZnO }	5680	1-0	1.247	0.935	0.519
26	Magenta } Do. + ZnO }	5840	1-0	1.818	1.091	0.753
27	Aniline Red } Do. + ZnO }	6160	1-0	2.203	1.091	1.040
28	Aniline yellow } Do. + ZnO }	5120	1-0	2.078	1.974	0.812
29	Auramine } Do. + ZnO }	4480	1-0	1.040	0.984	0.984
30	Methyl Orange } Do. + ZnO }	5040	1-0	2.727	2.857	1.948
31	Purpurin } Do. + ZnO }	5589	1-0	1.402	0.883	0.364
32	Tropacolin } Do. + ZnO }	5560	1-0	0.779	0.727	0.519

No.	Dyes.	Region in Å units.	Time H. M.	Extinction coeff. unexposed (dark).	Extinction coeff. exposed (sunlight).	Extinction coeff. exposed with ZnO (sunlight).
33	Aniline Scarlet } Do. + ZnO	5720	1-0	1.298	1.104	1.091
34	Theonine Grubber } Do. + ZnO	5860	1-0	1.039	.964	.863
35	Thioflavine } Do. + ZnO	5860	1-0	4.675	1.558	1.089
36	Corcus Red } Do. + ZnO	5240	1-0	1.091	.678	.623
37	Rosaniline } Do. + ZnO	5240	1-0	1.195	1.039	2.337*
38	Acridine Orange } Do. + ZnO	5860	1-0	2.340	2.078	1.948
39	Acridine Yellow } Do. + ZnO	5860	1-0	1.299	1.195	.987
40	Aesculin } Do. ZnO	5860	1-0	1.649	.597	.416

With alizarin blue and methyl orange, there is a slight increase in the concentration of the solutions after exposure to sunlight. This is due to the fact that these dyes are not oxidized at all by air in presence of sunlight and a little water is lost by evaporation from the solutions after exposure to air for an hour.

In diffused light there was no change in the colour of the dyes with zinc oxide. The bleaching of the dyes was noticeable in a short time when the solutions were exposed to sunlight with zinc oxide.

As a general behaviour it was found that the dyes which absorb light of longer wave-lengths and are of the type blue, green, violet, etc., are much accelerated in their bleaching in sunlight by zinc oxide. The next in order comes the fluorescent dyes which also absorb light of longer wave-lengths, and lastly are the dyes of red,

orange and yellow type which absorb light of shorter wave-lengths. There are only very few exceptions to the above generalisation which might be due to impurities.

In recent papers Baur and co-workers (*Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1924, 7, 910; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, Oct. 1925, p. 829) have investigated the sensitising influence of zinc oxide on the photochemical decomposition of an aqueous solution of silver nitrate and methylene blue in absence of air.

In the case of the decomposition of silver nitrate, Baur and Perret (*loc. cit.*) represented the process schematically as follows:—

We are of the opinion that this scheme of Baur is unsatisfactory, because there is no experimental evidence in support of the above views, and the decomposition of silver nitrate can be easily understood from the following considerations:—It is well known that salts of heavy metals like silver, gold, platinum etc., have a tendency to decompose and in presence of light, solutions of these salts decompose readily. In presence of zinc oxide this decomposition tendency of silver nitrate is increased.

We are of opinion that in presence of light the molecules of zinc oxide absorb the incident radiation and become activated. The activated molecules of zinc oxide come in contact with the molecules of silver nitrate and activate them by the transference of energy from the molecules of zinc oxide to those of silver nitrate. The decomposition of silver nitrate takes place according to the following equation:—

In addition to the sensitising effect, zinc oxide has also the function of neutralising the nitric acid which is set free and thus helps the decomposition of silver nitrate. We have observed that in presence of calcium carbonate, strontium carbonate etc., which also neutralise the free nitric acid, solutions of silver nitrate appreciably decompose in sunlight, but the effect of calcium carbonate, or strontium carbonate is not as great as that of zinc oxide which also acts as a marked photochemical sensitiser.

In a recent paper Chakravarti and Dhar (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, 142, 299) have shown that solutions of dyes are unstable in presence of light and they can be readily oxidised or reduced under suitable conditions. We have shown that in presence of air several dye solutions are readily oxidised in presence of light, and in this paper we have shown that this oxidation of dyes is markedly accelerated by zinc oxide. Moreover in the same paper Chakravarti and Dhar proved that the solutions of dyes can also decompose in presence of strong ultra-violet or sunlight just as solutions of potassium permanganate, potassium persulphate or ammonium nitrite decompose in presence of strong light. In this paper we have proved that the decomposition of potassium permanganate, potassium persulphate etc., in sunlight is accelerated by zinc oxide.

Baur has represented the photolysis of methylene blue in presence of zinc oxide when air is not present in the following way:—

We are however of the opinion that these dyes which are unstable substances decompose in sunlight in the same way as the solution of potassium permanganate does in sunlight. It is likely that the decomposition of dyes can in some cases be compared to the decomposition of nitrous acid, hypophosphorous acid, phosphorous acid etc., according to the following equations:—

The photochemical decomposition of nitrogen pentoxide has been found by Daniels and Johnston (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 58, 72) to be accelerated in visible light in presence of nitrogen dioxide. We are of opinion that nitrogen dioxide acts as a sensitiser in the photochemical decomposition of nitrogen pentoxide, just as chlorine sensitises the photochemical decomposition of ozone.

Further work on photo-sensitisation and photo-inhibition is in progress in these laboratories.